

Digital Agriculture Sandbox for Collaborative Research

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Abstract—Digital agriculture is transforming the way we grow food by utilizing technology to make farming more efficient, sustainable, and productive. This modern approach to agriculture generates a wealth of valuable data that could help address global food challenges, but farmers are hesitant to share it due to privacy concerns. This limits the extent to which researchers can learn from this data to inform improvements in farming. This paper presents the Digital Agriculture Sandbox, a secure online platform that solves this problem. The platform enables farmers (with limited technical resources) and researchers to collaborate on analyzing farm data without exposing private information. We employ specialized techniques such as federated learning, differential privacy, and data analysis methods to safeguard the data while maintaining its utility for research purposes. The system enables farmers to identify similar farmers in a simplified manner without needing extensive technical knowledge or access to computational resources. Similarly, it enables researchers to learn from the data and build helpful tools without the sensitive information ever leaving the farmer’s system. This creates a safe space where farmers feel comfortable sharing data, allowing researchers to make important discoveries. Our platform helps bridge the gap between maintaining farm data privacy and utilizing that data to address critical food and farming challenges worldwide.

Index Terms—Privacy Enhancing Technologies, Digital Agriculture, Privacy Preserving Framework, Secure Collaborative Research

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has been the cornerstone of human society and its evolution for thousands of years. Over the years, it evolved from basic hunting and gathering to large-scale planting and harvesting. In the era of digital innovation and data-driven evolution, digital agriculture is playing a vital role in driving productivity, aiding research, and evolving the entire field of agriculture. The large-scale use of electronic devices and machines in the agricultural sector has enabled the collection of a massive amount of data from fields and their utilization for research and development. Collected data is used to develop

next-generation seeds, highly effective fertilizers, insecticides, and pesticides, as well as to train machine learning models for irrigation management, disease detection, field monitoring, yield prediction, and various other research initiatives have transformed cultivation and harvest practices [1], [2]. However, due to the sensitive nature of the data generated and collected from the farms, farmers are hesitant to share it with anyone [3], [4]. The data can be easily leveraged against farmers, resulting in adverse consequences, such as insurance hikes, unfavorable pricing, discrimination, and resource manipulation [5]–[7]. This lack of access to farmers hinders research and development in the field. To unlock the full potential of agricultural data, access to small-scale farm data is paramount; thus, it is imperative to develop solutions that allow researchers to access the data they need in a privacy-preserving manner that protects and safeguards the privacy and livelihoods of farmers.

II. BACKGROUND

In this section, we define the specific terms being used in the remainder of the paper.

Federated learning is a machine learning technique where multiple entities collaboratively train a shared model without directly exchanging their raw data. Each entity trains a local model on its data and only shares model updates with a central server, which then aggregates these updates to improve the global model. Multiple rounds of local training and aggregation are done to train a well-generalized global model.

Model inference is the process of using a trained machine learning model to make predictions on new, unseen data. Black box access means that the end user only has access to query the trained model and receive output. They do not have access to the inner workings of the model, such as architecture and weights.

Membership inference is a type of attack on machine learning models, aimed at determining if a specific data point was used to train the target model. Such attacks exploit the

fact that models can sometimes retain information about their training data, allowing an attacker to infer whether a given data point was part of the training set.

III. DIGITAL AGRICULTURE FRAMEWORK

We developed a web-based privacy-preserving digital agriculture sandbox for farmers and researchers. It allows stakeholders (both farmers and researchers) to upload data to their accounts on the platform and perform collaborative operations on it in a secure and privacy-protected manner. The goal is to ensure the privacy and protection of data owners while allowing them (and other stakeholders, specifically researchers) to train machine learning models and gain analytical insights for research and development purposes. For simplicity, we will continue the discussion with the example of the farmers as stakeholders; however, both farmers and researchers have access to all functionalities and can perform all operations.

A. Sandbox's underlying architecture

Sandbox is based on the privacy-preserving data sharing and collaborative research architecture proposed in [8]. The proposed architecture combines techniques such as Principal Component Analysis [9], local differential privacy [10], [11], Laplacian noise addition [12], and federated learning to allow farmers to perform operations on distributed data in a privacy-preserving manner. Individual farmers upload farm data to their accounts, which is not shared with other farmers. However, computations such as identifying other farmers based on data similarities and training machine learning models on distributed data can be performed in a privacy-preserving manner. For more details on the architecture and privacy guarantees it provides, please refer to [8].

B. Key features

Identity management functionality enables users to access their accounts on the platform, upload and manage datasets, perform computational operations, and train models. We use the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) as the identity provider. Accounts can be created on their platform, and the same credentials can be used to access accounts on the sandbox.

Upload functionality allows farmers to upload data to their account on the sandbox (see Figure 1). Only the account owner has access to the data uploaded to it and can delete it at any time. To upload the data to the framework, the following prerequisites must be satisfied:

- Upload file must be in CSV (Comma Separated Values) file format.
- The upload file must have a column header. It's the first row that contains all the column names.
- The target column must be named 'label'.

To keep the process simplified for farmers with limited technical skills, CSV format is chosen because most IoT sensors, farm management systems, and agricultural devices directly export data in this well-known and widely used format.

Fig. 1: Illustrate the farm dataset upload user interface: users can input a dataset name and upload their farm data via the designated upload area, then confirm with 'Upload Dataset'.

The **Identify similar farmers** functionality enables farmers to identify and connect with other farmers who share similar characteristics in a privacy-preserving manner without sharing any raw farmer data using techniques introduced by [8]. The farmer (the initiator of the operation) selects a dataset from their list of upload datasets. Sandbox identifies other farmers (potential collaborators) based on the similarity between the initiator's dataset and their datasets. To ensure uniformity across similarity calculations, farmers with datasets having the same metadata as the initiator's dataset are considered for the similarity calculations. After calculating, an ordered list of farmer profiles (only usernames, no personal identifiers) is displayed in decreasing order of similarity.

Chat functionality enables farmers to communicate with "identifying similar farmers" on the platform, facilitating collaboration and knowledge sharing. Farmers can share information with each other based on their comfort level.

Collaborative model training functionality enables farmers to train machine learning models using data from other farmers in a privacy-preserving manner. This functionality leverages federated learning to enhance data privacy and security, as it allows models to be trained without sharing or centralizing sensitive data. To optimize the training process and reduce the number of participating collaborators (farmers), we utilize the "Identify Similar Farmers" functionality and select highly similar farmers to contribute to the model training process. This optimizes the training process by the number of collaborators without significant loss of model utility [8]. To submit a training request, follow these steps.

- Selecting reference dataset from uploaded datasets.
- Entering the name for the model.
- Selecting model type from the list of models available.
- Selecting model visibility, either public or private.
- Adding how-to instructions for the users.
- Selecting collaborators for training from the list of similar farmers.

Fig. 2: Illustrate the model training user interface: users can input a model name, define parameters like model type and visibility, add an optional readme, select collaborators, and then confirm with 'Start Training'.

All submitted model training jobs are executed in the background. Further discussion on model training can be found in Section III-C.

Model Repository functionality allows farmers to view available machine learning models. All models have a "model visibility" value set to either "public" or "private". Models with public model visibility are visible to everyone on the platform; however, private models are only visible to the model owner and their designated contacts. All models have the following intractable feature available through the platform:

- The information component is accessible by clicking on the info icon, which displays the model's general information, including: model Name, model type, metadata, model owner, model visibility, number of classes, class name, and training status.
- Risk quantification component is accessible by clicking on the red shield icon, which displays model inference and risk analysis information such as:
 - Model logs show the number of inference queries made by each user and their inference risk score.
 - Model activity shows individual inference requests with information about the sender, time, and number of queries.
 - Risk analysis provides the overall risk score for the

model, along with a plot illustrating the risk scoring for all users interacting with the model.

- The Playground component is accessible by clicking on the play icon, which allows farmers to interact with the model by submitting their data and receiving the model's output. It provides general information on how to submit data for model inference, along with the 'how-to-use' instructions from the model owner, which can be downloaded by clicking the download icon in the top right corner of the card.

C. Deployment

The sandbox environment is a Docker containerized application comprising five containers: frontend, database, application server, parameter server, and farmer server. Figure 3 shows how deployed containers interact with each other. In the following sections, we provide detailed descriptions of individual containers.

- Frontend container, serves the web pages and allows the farmers to interact with the platform.
- A database container is used to host a MongoDB server, which stores databases that house uploaded datasets, models, chats, logs, and other information.
- Application server container hosts a Flask server, which serves as the core of the application, responsible for all authentication, request orchestration, and computations. It does not have direct access to any of the farmer data or models. It sends requests to the parameter server or farmer server to perform computations on the user's raw data.
- Farmer server, executes computations on the farmer's behalf. It loads farmers' data, executes their local computations on their behalf, and deletes all information after the computations are done. It digitally segregates information from different farmers and keeps all information distributed as if it were physically distributed. This provides a privacy guarantee that only farmers have access to their data, and their data is never stored or processed with that of other farmers. Upon request, the farmer server is responsible for training local machine learning models on individual farmers' data, sharing updates to the parameter server, and also computing membership inference risk for trained models.
- Parameter server is used to execute model training jobs. Jobs are submitted to the parameter server by the application server, which then orchestrates the training of local models for all collaborators. With the farmer server, it receives model updates and aggregates them to save the final model weights. It also computes risk analysis for a trained model by interacting with the farmer server.

Technologies were selected solely based on technical considerations. The application is containerized with Docker, allowing effortless deployment across various cloud providers like GCP, Azure, AWS, or on private local servers without concerns about dependency management or technical skills.

Fig. 3: Illustrates the deployment of the sandbox within a containerized environment and the interaction among the containers.

Likewise, MongoDB was chosen for its capacity to manage unstructured data, but it can easily be replaced with any other database.

D. Use Cases

The sandbox platform enables farmers to share sensitive data, addressing their privacy concerns securely. It allows farmers to discover and connect with like-minded individuals, fostering collaboration while maintaining their data privacy. This promotes effective sharing, learning, and development of best practices. For researchers and stakeholders, the platform offers tools to securely identify collaborators and train machine learning models with distributed data. This unlocks new research possibilities, accelerates innovation, and enhances understanding in the agricultural sector.

IV. FUTURE WORK

In the future, we plan to integrate additional features to support research and development in the field. We plan to expand functionalities across different components of the sandbox. The following are the details of potential expansions:

- In the model training component, we plan to extend the list of available trainable machine learning models, training customizations, and hyperparameter tuning.
- In the playground component, we plan to provide additional information with the inference results, such as model explanations and model confidence.
- In the risk quantification component, we plan to integrate more risk quantification algorithms, additional risk analysis information associated explicitly with model explanations, and model confidence.
- In similarity identification, there is a potential risk of social engineering attacks by malicious actors, such as insurance companies, attempting to upload datasets and identify similar farmers to deanonymize them through chat functionality. We plan to add safeguards through identity verification during the onboarding process.
- We intend to develop a data-sharing component that enables farmers to share their datasets with researchers

while ensuring the protection of their privacy. This will be accomplished through the implementation of techniques designed to remove personal identifiers and achieve differential privacy.

V. CONCLUSION

The promise of digital agriculture's innovation in the field to feed the world's population is hindered by concerns over data privacy. Our web-based digital agriculture sandbox addresses this by offering a privacy-preserving framework for collaborative knowledge sharing and research.

Leveraging innovative techniques, the privacy-preserving collaborative framework, federated learning, differential privacy, and PCA, the sandbox enables secure similarity calculations and model training. Its features, including identity management, secure uploads, farmer similarity identification, chat, and collaborative model training, create a trusted environment. The modular, containerized deployment ensures robustness. This platform serves as a vital science gateway, offering researchers access to distributed agricultural data, accelerating innovation, and fostering a collaborative ecosystem for farmers. The digital agriculture sandbox is a significant step towards unlocking the full potential of agricultural data for secure and impactful research.

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